
64. Solar system objects

ALTHOUGH MODEST in number, the few solar system objects measured from space by Hipparcos (between 1989–1993) secured the importance and huge potential of observing solar system objects with Gaia.

For Hipparcos, all objects to be observed had to be selected pre-launch. At each measurement epoch, solar system objects had to be brighter than 12–13 mag, and smaller than 1 arcsec in angular diameter, while planetary satellites also had to be sufficiently far from their host planet to be unaffected by scattered light.

As a result, Hipparcos observed just 48 asteroids, from (1) Ceres to (704) Interamnia, and just three satellites: Jupiter's Europa, and Saturn's Titan and Iapetus. A few others, including Uranus and Neptune, and Jupiter's Ganymede and Callisto, were observed as part of the star-mapper Tycho Catalogue (Hestroffer et al. 1998).

One goal in observing these objects was to provide a dynamical reference frame based on the absence of rotation in their equations of motion. Masses, from orbit perturbations due to close encounters, notably for Massalia–Nysa (Bange 1998), as well as photometric inferences, such as limb darkening and rotational-induced variability, were also obtained (e.g. Hestroffer 1998).

A 7-PAGE REVIEW OF Gaia's predicted capabilities, included in the Concept & Technology study (Perryman et al. 2000), demonstrated the enormous scope of Gaia's expected contributions to solar system science.

The on-board detection of all objects brighter than 20–21 mag would yield a deep and uniform detection of minor planets and other solar system bodies (including near-Earth asteroids and Kuiper belt objects), permitting profound studies of their dynamics, structure, and taxonomy. This is important because these minor bodies retain a record of the conditions in the proto-solar nebula, and their properties therefore shed light on the formation and evolution of our solar system.

As well as known objects, Gaia was also predicted to discover upwards of 100 000 new objects, including the difficult inner Trojans, with extremely precise orbits derived from multiple observations over several years.

TO DATE, Gaia Data Release 2 (DR2), made available in April 2018, and based on observations between July 2014 and May 2016, provided limited data on around 14 000 asteroids. Early Data Release 3 (EDR3), provided no further updates on solar system objects.

Gaia DR3 will provide a further major update in mid-2022, including astrometry (and some orbits) for around 150 000 asteroids, along with an unprecedented spectral survey for more than 60 000 objects, with enormous possibilities for taxonomic and dynamical investigations.

WHILE IT IS TOO SOON to have much visibility of the impact that Gaia will have on their understanding, important 'hints' are beginning to appear.

At least for near-Earth asteroids, Gaia is providing positional accuracies close to that from radar ranging. And new alerts are being published as part of a dedicated follow-up network of some 100 observers around the world, leading to further improvements in orbits.

This combination of DR2 asteroid orbits, and star positions for more than 2 billion objects, is having a significant impact on stellar occultations, where robotic telescopes and international collaborations are leading to some fascinating progress (essay #60). Amongst these are early results related to the minor planet *Carnegie* in 2016; of the ringed-Centaur *Chariklo* in 2017; and of Neptune's *Triton* in 2018.

Timing uncertainties are now becoming sensitive to knowledge of the object's size, shape, and spin properties, which are, in turn, being improved by the occultations themselves (Ferreira et al. 2020; 2022).

In a preview of the DR3 results, Tanga (2021) has reported the discovery of the Yarkovsky acceleration (due to the anisotropic emission of thermal photons) amongst 20 new discoveries, and the photocentric wobble of 4337 *Arecibo*, the first asteroid for which a satellite has been discovered by occultations.

And Delbo et al. (2021) have shown that reflectance spectra, from B_p and R_p photometry, will probe the composition gradient of the main belt even down to small object sizes.

NOTWITHSTANDING their scientific importance, solar system bodies present specific challenges for the data processing, mainly because of their significant proper motions. In the remainder of this essay I'll look at how these tasks are organised within the overall Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium.

The processing of satellite data leading to the successive data releases is organised broadly as a 'wheel and spoke' system: the satellite data arrives at the ESAC centre outside Madrid, where source matching, and the astrometric global iterative solution (AGIS), are executed.

A number of other 'coordination units' take these data, and subject them to various specialised tasks, generally conducted at other processing centres across Europe. Their results are returned to ESAC, and all processes are iterated, making use of the intermediate outputs of the other processing tasks as appropriate, including photometric calibration and variability analysis.

Within this framework, Coordination Unit 4 (CU4) treats three specific objects types: binary and multiple systems including exoplanets (originally led by Dimitri Pourbaix[‡], Bruxelles, but since 2021 by Frédéric Arenou, Paris–Meudon); extended objects (Christine Ducourant, Bordeaux), and solar system objects (Paolo Tanga, Nice).

The solar system objects group comprises about 25 people (mainly from Paris, Helsinki, and Bruxelles), with the computations undertaken by a team from the French national space agency (CNES, Toulouse). The paper detailing the treatment of solar system objects for DR2 had 450 authors (Spoto et al. 2018), illustrating the extensive interconnectivity of the data analysis.

PRESENT PREDICTIONS are that, by mission end, Gaia will have observed 350 000 solar system objects at multiple epochs, many of them new. For Gaia DR2, a subset of 14 099 known objects, with known orbits, were extracted from the data stream for publication.

This involved nearly 300 000 focal-plane transits, and nearly 2 million individual CCD observations, observed over the first 22 months of the mission. Because of the scanning law, solar system objects are only observed at solar elongations between 45 – 135°. Observations are otherwise well-distributed on the sky.

As well as having reasonably well-known orbits (facilitating object matching), these 'showcase' objects were selected to represent most main dynamical classes, including main-belt asteroids (MBA), near-Earth objects (NEO), Jupiter Trojans, and a number of trans-Neptunian objects (TNO).

The data processing for solar system objects mostly follows the procedures in place for star observations: positional coordinates in the instrument's focal plane are converted into sky coordinates by using the transformations provided by AGIS, the astrometric global iterative solution, along with the corresponding calibrations.

COORDINATE TRANSFORMATIONS include proceeding from a non-rotating reference system (with its origin in the satellite's centre of mass) to the barycentric reference system (with its origin at the solar system barycentre), including the rigorous effects of general relativistic light bending by the Sun.

Resulting astrometry yields a single-transit accuracies below 1 milli-arcsec for objects with $G < 17.5$, and still better than 2–5 milli-arcsec for the faintest observable ($G \sim 20.5$). Although this accuracy is essentially in one-dimension (in the direction of the scan motion), the 'imprint' of the scanning law largely vanishes when several transits, in different scan directions, are combined.

Photometry for all objects, stars as well as solar system objects, is provided at focal-plane transit level by the photometric processing coordination unit. A specific complication for solar system objects is due to their large proper motion: within a focal plane transit, exposure times (4.4 s) are determined by the crossing of a single CCD. An object with an apparent motion (in the along-scan direction) of merely 13.6 milli-arcsec/s moves by one pixel during a single CCD crossing, leading to noticeable image smearing.

Orbit determination then uses a least-squares adjustment, starting with the previously known orbit elements, and employing the positions of the major solar system bodies from the JPL DE431 planetary ephemerides, to take account of gravitational terms due to the Sun, the major planets, the Moon, and Pluto, and a further sixteen massive main-belt asteroids.

THE RESULTING DISTRIBUTION of orbital eccentricity (e) versus semi-major axis (a) for the 14 099 solar system objects included in Gaia DR2, shown here, clearly distinguishes the near-Earth asteroid population from the main-belt asteroids (including the Jupiter Trojans), and the trans-Neptunian objects.

Extending these results to simulations representing longer data sets, Spoto et al. (2018) have shown that Gaia should eventually lead to an improvement (with respect to the pre-Gaia orbits) of nearly a factor 10 in the orbital elements of typical main-belt asteroids for a 5-year mission, to around a factor 20 for a 10-year mission.

With this vast network of astrometric measurements of unprecedented accuracy, the Gaia orbit accuracies will, in turn, far exceed those obtained even after decades of orbit-tracking from the ground.

Spoto et al. (2018)